

- Lineages**
- Termite-associated *Bifidobacteriaceae*
 - Actinomycetota*
 - Verrucomicrobiota*
 - Alphaproteobacteria*
 - Enterobacterales*
 - Bacilli*
 - Bacteroidota*
 - Endomicrobiia*
 - Elusimicrobia*
 - Chlamydiota*
 - Oscillospirales*
 - Planctomycetota*
 - Desulfobacterota*
 - biochem. characterized